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OIL POLLUTION AT SEA AND EFFECTS ON THE FAUNA

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THE AIM OF THE PROJECT

- IDENTIFY OIL POLLUTION
- CAUSES
- EFFECT ON FAUNA
- PREVENTION

WHAT IS OIL

- OILS(CRUDE OIL + PRODUCTS)
- GAS, SOLID OR LIQUID
- HYDROCARBONS
- OXYGEN, NITROGEN, SULFUR
- METALS

Water solubilities of different hydrocarbons containing six carbons

Compound	Structure	Aqueous Solubility	
		(g m ⁻³)	(mole m ⁻³)
n-Hexane	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₄ CH ₃	9.5	0.11
2-Methylpentane	$\begin{array}{c} \text{CH}_3\text{CH}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{CH}_3 \\ \\ \text{CH}_3 \end{array}$	13.8	0.16
Cyclohexane		55	0.65
Benzene		1780	22.8

Refinery processes

Physical and chemical properties of crude oil

Characteristic /Component	Unit/reference measured	Value
Specific gravity	15/15°C	0.80-0.988
Initial boiling point	°C	30-125
Kinematic viscosity	cS, 100°F	4-25
Pour point	°C	-35-7.0
Sulphur	% wt	0.80-5.00
Wax	% wt	5-12
Asphaltenes	% wt	0.05-3.00

CRUDE OILS

- LIGHT CRUDE OIL
 - $API > 20^\circ$
 - HEAVY CRUDE OIL
 - $API < 20^\circ$
 - BITUMENS
 - $API < 10^\circ$
 - EXTRA CRUDE OIL
 - $API < 10^\circ$ including bitumens
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THE ECOSYSTEM OF THE ARCTIC SEA

THE TOXICITY OF PETROLEUM

The toxicity of petroleum measured as LC 50 values

Organism class	Range of LC50 values (mg/L)
Fin fish	1-50
Crustaceans	0.1-10
Bivalves	1-50
Gastropods	1-100
Larvae(all species)	0.1-5
Juveniles(all species)	1-10

CAUSES AND SOURCES OF THE POLLUTION

The incident of global oil spills by cause, 1974-1999

	<7 (tonnes)	7-700 (tonnes)	>700 (tonnes)	Total
OPERATIONS				
Loading/Discharging	2759 (90%)	294 (9%)	17 (1%)	3070
Bunkering	541 (95%)	25 (5%)	0	566
Other Operations	1162 (96%)	47 (4%)	0	1209
ACCIDENTS				
Collisions	153 (32%)	236 (50%)	86 (18%)	475
Groundings	219 (42%)	196 (37%)	103 (21%)	518
Hull Failures	555 (82%)	73 (10%)	43 (8%)	671
Fire & Explosions	149 (80%)	16 (8%)	19 (12%)	184
Other	2214 (92%)	162 (6%)	35 (2%)	2411
TOTAL	7752 (85%)	1049 (11%)	303 (4%)	9104

KNOWN POLLUTION INCIDENTS

- USA
 - Argo Merchant(16TH DECEMBER 1976)
 - 27300 tones No. 6 fuel oil
- CANADA
 - Gordon C. Leitch(March 1999)
 - 49 tones bunker oil

EFFECT OF OIL ON FAUNA

- KIND OF OIL
- BIRDS
 - COATING->DESTRUCTION OF THE WATERPROOF PLUMAGE->LOSS OF BODY TEMPERATURE->(DEATH).
- FISH
 - GALL BLADDER,GUT, LIVER AND BRAIN.
- MARINE MAMMALS
 - SURFACE COATING/ ORAL INGESTION->THERMAL STRESS,WEAKENED SWIMMING ABILITY AND DISEASES.
 - SEALS : STRESS, EYE IRRITATION, NO TEMPERATURE CHANGE
 - OIL INGESTION BELOW 75ML->NO NEGATIVE IMPACT
 - WHALES:
 - NO NEGATIVE IMPACT THAN EYE IRRITATION

DAMAGE ASSESSMENT AND RESTORATION OF WILDLIFE

LIMITING THE SPREAD OF THE OIL

- BOOMS
 - floating Barriers, fence.
- Alarm systems for detecting oil spilled
 - Infrared device: warning
 - Spill sentry : Valve controlling systems

REMOVING SPILLED OIL

- MECHANICALLY
 - SKIMMERS
 - SUCKING (ROCKS)
 - CHEMICALLY
 - BURNING, SINKING, DISPERSANTS, HERDING AGENTS, SORPTION, GELLING.
 - PHYSICALLY
 - MANPOWER + OTHER METHODS
 - BIOLOGICALLY
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(a) ROTATING NONPOROUS BELT

(b) OLEOPHILIC DISC

(c) HYDRO-ADJUSTABLE OVERFLOW WEIR

(d) SIMPLE OVERFLOW WEIR

(e) ROTATING POROUS BELT

(f) ADVANCING WEIR

(g) DOUBLE ADVANCING WEIR

PREVENTION OF THE POLLUTION

- INTERNATIONAL LAWS AND CONVECTIONS
 - HEAVIER BOOMS FOR PERMANENT USE
 - FORBIDDEN AREAS
 - 100 MILES FROM NEAREST LAND

 - PREVENTION IN TANKERS
 - THE BOW

 - NAVIGATIONAL SYSTEMS
 - RISK ASSESSMENT
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SUGGESTION TO AVOID OIL SPILL

- ALTERNATIVE TRANSPORT SYSTEMS
- INSTALLATION OF ALCOHOL METER
- INTERNATIONAL RESCUE TEAMS
- SHIP OWNERS RESPONSIBILITIES

CONCLUSION

- OIL
- AROMATICS MORE TOXIC THAN OTHER HYDROCARBONS
- CHEMICAL REMOVAL
- COLLISIONS AND GROUNDINGS

THANK YOU

THE END

